

ASSESSMENT OF MUSCULOSKELETAL PROBLEMS EXPERIENCED WHILE PERFORMING LIME HARVESTING ACTIVITY WITH SELECTED LIME HARVESTERS BY FARM WOMEN

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Abstract

The present study entitled “Assessment of musculoskeletal problems experienced while performing lime harvesting activity with selected lime harvesters by farm women” was carried out in large number of lime growing fields from Rawalgaon, Itlapur and Makhni villages of Parbhani District of Marathwada region in Maharashtra state, because participation of women in lime harvesting activity was observed maximum in these selected villages. A random sample of 30 farm women who were involved in lime harvesting activity since 5 years was selected for the study. Two harvester were selected for the study i.e. Traditional lime harvester and new developed lime harvester by AICRP-WIA, Dept. of Resource Management and Consumer Science, College of Community Science, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra.

Results of the study indicated that selected farm women experienced very severe pain in neck, shoulder and low back while harvesting lime by traditional lime harvester and experienced very light pain in low back while harvesting limes by new improved lime harvester. Symptoms frequency score were indicated highest in case of harvesting lime by traditional lime harvester for hands & wrists, ankles & feet, followed by neck and low back. Whereas symptom frequency scores were indicated, highest in case of harvesting by new improved lime harvester for neck and hand & wrists. Symptom frequency score was low for low back. Regarding body tolerance to these symptoms was unbearable for the selected body parts in the activity of lime harvesting by traditional lime harvester and when harvesting by new improved method, body tolerance to these symptoms was unbearable for the selected body parts i.e. neck, shoulder, upper arm and upper back body tolerance symptoms was bearable for hand & wrist and ignorable for low back.

Key words: Lime, Harvester, Musculoskeletal problems

Introduction

Mechanized harvesting is recognized as the most promising area of intervention to tackle increasing phenomena of labour scarcity and costs and to fuel farm prosperity and entrepreneurial opportunity in the rural part of the country (Rickman et al., 2013). Most of the Indian farmers practicing conventional hand-picking methods for fruit harvesting. However, conventional methods are inefficient and more importantly results in deterioration of fruit quality and fruit damage (Mlotek et al., 2015)

Results indicated that work related musculoskeletal problems and disorders affect all the parts of body viz. hands, wrists, elbow, shoulder and back in upper body region, hips, knees, and calf muscles in lower body region. In the home and farm where women performs tasks while sitting, standing, bending, twisting, awkward posture, duration of work and inadequate rest pause were associated with the occurrence of serious musculoskeletal problems and disorders (Suthar and Kaushik, 2011)

To effectively prevent musculoskeletal disorders, it is necessary to identify risk factor for work and to take concrete measures to prevent or reduce risks. Compared to other industries, economic interventions and solutions have been late coming into agriculture. Several examples of changing the interface between worker and his and/or her workplace have been shown to hold promise in reducing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders among agricultural workers. This approach is usually achieved by providing alternative tools or alters the work space to reduce the risk of awkward postures.

Many tools have been developed to reduce the amount of bending required from agricultural carrying heavy loads by hand is strenuous and very awkward. As in other industries, but particularly in agriculture, effective ergonomic intervention must be developed and implemented using a team approach and as a part of comprehensive risk management approach, workers participation in developing economic intervention in agriculture is paramount in providing the crucial feedback on efficiency, comfort, and socio-cultural issue that many affect worker acceptance and understand the barriers to the adoption.

Keeping this in mind the study is initiated with the following objectives.

Objectives

To assess musculoskeletal problems experienced while performing lime harvesting activity with selected lime harvesters by farm women.

To know the symptom frequency score of musculoskeletal problems while performing lime harvesting activity with selected lime harvesters by farm women.

To know the body tolerance to symptoms while performing lime harvesting activity with selected lime harvesters by farm women.

Methodology

The present study was carried out in large number of lime growing fields from Rawalgaon, Itlapur and Makhni villages of Parbhani District of Marathwada region in Maharashtra state, because participation of women in lime harvesting activity was observed maximum in these selected villages. A random sample of 30 farm women who were involved in lime harvesting activity since 5 years was selected for the study.

Traditional lime harvester

Traditional lime harvester had 96 inch long bamboo handle. To the handle iron hook is fixed at one end. Locally this iron hook is called as ‘Kudi’ used to harvest the limes from the branches. While harvesting limes with the help of Kudi limes fall on the ground and damage. Women had to collect these limes from the ground in bucket or basket.

Details of the newly developed lime harvester is as follow.

Newly developed lime harvester is developed in AICRP-WIA, Department of Resource Management and Consumer Science, VNMKV, Parbhani.

Construction of the lime harvester

The Lime collector and lime collecting cap

Lime collector is made up of PVC pipe having 4” diameter having 10” length. ‘V’ shape triangle cut having equal sides (4”) was made on the lime collecting pipe to catch the limes inside the cutter. On the upper side of the lime collecting pipe with the help of 1mm diameter MS wire, lime cutter blade is made. With the help of cutter, limes cut and drop in to the lime collecting cap.

Handle

One inch diameter PVC pipe having 54" length is attached with the help of two nuts to the lower end of the lime collecting pipe.

Plate No. 1 : Traditional lime harvester

A: Iron hook (Kudi)

B: Bamboo handle

Plate No. 2: Newly designed lime harvester by AICRP-FRM

A: Lime collecting pipe

B: Handle of the harvester

C: Lime collecting cap

D: Lime cutter blade made up of MS Wire

E: Harvested lime with the help of blade

F: 'V' shape cut made on the lime collecting pipe to lock the lime inside the cutter

Survey

The study was comprised of survey to find out detailed information of the farm women and asking them a series of questions to collect information through personal interview method. A questionnaire was prepared to collect the details regarding farm women, harvester, and musculoskeletal problems. The experiment was conducted in the month of November 2023.

Assessment of musculoskeletal problems, symptom frequency score and body tolerance to symptoms

Incidences of musculoskeletal problems of the subjects were identified by using the body map viz. eye, neck, shoulders, upper arm, upper back wrists, lower back, muscles, and ankles and feet. The incidence of symptom frequency score and body tolerance to symptoms were recorded after the completion of the activity. The intensity of pain in the above stated parts of the body was recorded by using following scale having a five point scale (Ranjwan 2000).

Mean scores of musculoskeletal problems indicated that majority of farm women had sever pain in neck, shoulder and low back followed by upper arm and upper back

Results

Assessment of musculoskeletal problems of the selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester

Assessment of musculoskeletal problems of the selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester are presented in table 1. Musculoskeletal problems experienced by farm women were assessed with the help of body map while performing the lime harvesting with traditional lime harvester. It can be assessed from table 1 that major musculoskeletal problems while performing lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester as reported by selected 40 per cent female workers had very severe pain in the neck and shoulder, where 53.33 per cent and 40 per cent farm women experienced moderate pain in Ankles & Feet and Hands & Wrists respectively. Also 36.66 per cent and 33.33 per cent experienced moderate pain in Upper Back and Upper arm respectively.

a) Symptom score

Scale	Score
Very Severe	5
Severe	4
Moderate	3
Light	2
Very light	1

b) Symptom frequency score

Scale	Score
Never	1
Rarely	2
Sometimes	3
Very often	4
Always	5

c) Body tolerance to symptoms

Scale	Score
Ignorable	1
Bearable	2
Unbearable	3

Assessment of musculoskeletal problems of the selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by new improved lime harvester

Assessment of musculoskeletal problems of the selected farm women while performing lime harvesting activity by new improved lime harvester are presented in table 2. It is clear from the table that majority of farm women (33.33%) experienced very severe pain in neck, followed by shoulder (30%), where as 50 per cent, and 43.33 per cent of farm women experienced moderate pain in upper arm, and ankles & feet respectively. Equal per cent (40%) of farm women experienced moderate pain in shoulder and hands & wrist. About 53.33 per cent farm women experienced very light pain in low back. Mean scores of musculoskeletal problems indicated that majority of farm women had serve pain in neck and shoulder fallowed by upper arm and upper back.

Symptom frequency score of musculoskeletal problems of selected farm women performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester

Symptom frequency score of musculoskeletal problems of selected women performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester has been indicated in table 3. Body parts that were considered for symptoms frequency score and body tolerance to symptoms were neck, shoulder, upper arm, upper back, low back, hands & wrists and ankles & feet .

It is clear from the table that the average symptoms frequency score i.e 3.5 was higher in case of hands & wrist and ankles & feet. It was fallowed by 3.4 score for neck and low back and 3.2 score for shoulder and upper arm fallowed by upper back 3.0 score. It indicated that farm women experienced musculoskeletal symptoms very often while performing lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester.

Symptom frequency score of musculoskeletal problems of selected farm women performing the lime harvesting activity by new improved lime harvester

Symptom frequency score and body tolerance to symptoms of selected farm women performing lime harvesting activity by new improved lime harvester has been indicated in table 4. It is clear from the table that the average symptoms frequency scores i.e 3.3 was highest for neck and hands & wrist, fallowed by equal score 3.1 for shoulder and upper arm, and 3.0 for upper back and ankles & feet. Average symptoms frequency score was low for low back i.e 1.8

Body tolerance to symptoms by selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester

Body tolerance to symptoms by selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester has been indicated in table 5. Body tolerance to symptoms was measured on a three point scale i.e ignorable, bearable and unbearable symptoms with corresponding scale rating 1, 2 and 3 was noted. On an average body tolerance to symptoms score was in the range of 2.1 to 2.6 for the body parts neck ,shoulder, upper arm ,upper back, low back, hand & wrist and ankles & feet. It indicated that majority of the farm women, expressed that body tolerance to these symptoms was unbearable in the activity of lime harvesting by traditional lime harvester.

Body tolerance to symptoms by selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by new improved lime harvester

Body tolerance to symptoms by selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by new improved lime harvester has been presented in table 6. On an average body tolerance to symptoms score was in the range of 1.3 to 2.6 for the body parts neck, shoulder, upper arm, upper back, low back, hand & wrist and ankles & feet. The score of body tolerance symptoms regarding neck, shoulder, upper arm and upper back were in the category of unbearable. Majority of farm women felt that severity of pain was unbearable on the day when the harvesting activity was carried out continuously for 4 hours.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that selected farm women experienced very severe pain in neck, shoulder and low back while harvesting lime by traditional lime harvester and experienced very severe pain in neck and shoulder. Whereas very light pain in low back while harvesting limes by new improved lime harvester. Symptoms frequency score were indicated highest in case of harvesting lime by traditional lime harvester for hands & wrists, ankles & feet, followed by neck and law back. Whereas symptom frequency scores were indicated, highest in case of harvesting by new improved lime harvester for neck and hand & wrists. Symptom frequency score was low for low back. Regarding body tolerance to these symptoms was unbearable for the selected body parts in the activity of lime harvesting by traditional lime harvester and when harvesting by new improved method body tolerance to these symptoms was unbearable for the selected body parts i.e. neck, shoulder, upper arm and upper back, body tolerance symptoms was bearable for hand & wrist and ignorable for low back.

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Table 1: Assessment of musculoskeletal problems of the selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester

Severity of Pain	Musculoskeletal Problems						
	Neck	Shoulder	Upper arm	Upper Back	Low Back	Hands & Wrists	Ankles & Feet
Very severe	12(40)	12 (40)	8.(26.66)	8 (26.66)	10(33.33)	8.(26.66)	8.(26.66)
Severe	8(26.66)	4(13.33)	7(23.33)	6 (20)	8.(26.66)	-	-
Moderate	6(20)	10(33.33)	10(33.33)	11 (36.66)	8.(26.66)	12(40)	16(53.33)
Light	-	-	-	-	-	5(16.66)	3(10)
Very Light	4(13.33)	4(13.33)	5(16.66)	5 (16.66)	4(13.33)	5(16.66)	3(10)
Total Score	114	110	103	102	110	91	97
Mean \pm SD	3.8 \pm 1.31	3.6 \pm 1.34	3.4 \pm 1.35	3.4 \pm 1.35	3.6 \pm 1.29	3.0 \pm 1.37	3.2 \pm 1.25
Results	IV	IV	III	III	IV	I	II

Figures in parenthesis indicates per centages

Table 2: Assessment of musculoskeletal problems of the selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by improved lime harvester (N=30)

Severity of Pain	Musculoskeletal Problems						
	Neck	Shoulder	Upper arm	Upper Back	Low Back	Hands & Wrists	Ankles & Feet
Very severe	10(33.33)	9 (30)	7(23.33)	6 (20)	-	7(23.33)	6(20)
Severe	8(26.66)	5 (16.66)	4(13.33)	5 (16.66)	2(6.66)	-	-
Moderate	8(26.66)	12(40)	15(50)	10 (33.33)	2(6.66)	12(40)	13(43.33)
Light	-	-	-	4 (13.33)	10(33.33)	5(16.66)	5(16.66)
Very Light	4(13.33)	4(13.33)	4(13.33)	5 (16.66)	16(53.33)	5(16.66)	6(20)
Total Score	110	105	100	93	50	86	85
Mean \pm SD	3.6 \pm 1.29	4.1 \pm 1.3	3.3 \pm 1.2	3.06 \pm 1.31	1.6 \pm 0.86	2.9 \pm 1.37	2.8 \pm 1.31
Rank	IV	IV	III	III	I	II	II

Figures in parenthesis indicates per centages

Table 3: Symptom frequency score of the musculoskeletal problems of selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester (N=30)

Severity of Pain	Musculoskeletal Problems						
	Neck	Shoulder	Upper arm	Upper back	Low Back	Hands & Wrists	Ankles & Feet
Very severe	8.(26.66)	7(23.33)	7(23.33)	7 (23.33)	7 (23.33)	8.(26.66)	8.(26.66)
Severe	7(23.33)	1.(3.33)	1.(3.33)	3 (10)	6 (20)	8.(26.66)	8.(26.66)
Moderate	10(33.33)	16(53.33)	16(53.33)	14 (46.66)	10 (33.33)	9(30)	8.(26.66)
Light	-	3(10)	3(10)	3 (10)	7 (23.33)	3(10)	3(10)
Very Light	5(16.66)	3(10)	3(10)	3 (10)	-	2(6.66)	3(10)
Total Score	103	96	96	98	103	107	105
Mean \pm SD	3.4 \pm 1.35	3.2 \pm 1.21	3.2 \pm 1.21	3.0 \pm 1.23	3.4 \pm 1.08	3.5 \pm 1.19	3.5 \pm 1.27
Results	Very often	Very often	Very often	Very often	Very often	Very often	Very often

Figures in parenthesis indicates per centages

Table 4: Symptom frequency score of the musculoskeletal problems of selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by Improved lime harvester (N=30)

Severity of Pain	Musculoskeletal Problems						
	Neck	Shoulder	Upper arm	Upper back	Low Back	Hands & Wrists	Ankles & Feet
Very severe	7(23.33)	7(23.33)	7(23.33)	5 (16.66)	-	7(23.33)	6(20)
Severe	8.(26.66)	1.(3.33)	1.(3.33)	6 (20)	-	8 (26.66)	6(20)
Moderate	8.(26.66)	15(50)	14(46.66)	10 (33.33)	3(10)	8 (26.66)	6(20)
Light	2(6.66)	4(13.33)	4(13.33)	4 (13.33)	18(60)	2 (6.66)	8.(26.66)
Very Light	5(16.66)	3(10)	4(13.33)	5 (16.66)	9(30)	5 (16.66)	4(13.33)
Total Score	100	95	93	92	54	100	92
Mean \pm SD	3.3 \pm 1.3	3.1 \pm 1.23	3.1 \pm 1.29	3.0 \pm 1.28	1.8 \pm 0.610	3.3 \pm 1.3	3.0 \pm 1.36
Results	Very often	Very often	Very often	Very often	Rarely	Very often	Very often

Figures in parenthesis indicates per centages

Table 5: Body tolerance to symptoms by selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by traditional lime harvester (N=30)

Severity of Pain	Body tolerance score while performing lime harvesting						
	Neck	Shoulder	Upper arm	Upper back	Low Back	Hands & Wrists	Ankles & Feet
Ignorable	-	2(6.66)	2(6.66)	3	-	3(10)	4(13.33)
Bearable	10(33.33)	14(46.66)	14(46.66)	19	14(46.66)	20(66.66)	19(63.33)
Unbearable	20(66.66)	14(46.66)	14(46.66)	8	16(53.33)	7(23.33)	7(23.33)
Total Score	80	72	72	65	76	64	63
Mean \pm SD	2.6 \pm 0.47	2.4 \pm 0.62	2.4 \pm 0.62	2.1 \pm 0.57	2.5 \pm 0.50	2.1 \pm 0.57	2.1 \pm 0.59
Results	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable

Figures in parenthesis indicates per centages

Table 6: Body tolerance to symptoms by selected farm women while performing the lime harvesting activity by improved lime harvester (N=30)

Severity of Pain	Body tolerance score while performing lime harvesting						
	Neck	Shoulder	Upper arm	Upper back	Low Back	Hands & Wrists	Ankles & Feet
Ignorable	-	3(10)	3(10)	3 (10)	20(66.66)	6(20)	6(20)
Bearable	10(33.33)	13(43.33)	13(43.33)	13 (43.33)	10(33.33)	17(56.66)	17(56.66)
Unbearable	20(66.66)	14(46.66)	14(46.66)	14 (46.66)	-	7(23.33)	7(23.33)
Total Score	80	71	71	71	40	55	55
Mean \pm SD	2.6 \pm 0.47	2.3 \pm 0.66	2.3 \pm 0.66	2.3 \pm 0.66	1.3 \pm 0.95	1.8 \pm 0.66	1.8 \pm 0.66
Results	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable	Unbearable	Ignorable	Bearable	Bearable

Figures in parenthesis indicates per centages